

2023 Brian Kaess Family Halloween Message

Greetings from Mexico! We have enjoyed the beautiful, bright sunshine during the past year. Mayte has been busy attempting to sell houses and tending to her family. She also helped decorate the front of our development & house with Halloween stuff. Paul spent the Summer in Chicago cultivating his artistic talents. He made it back to Puebla in the Fall to start his 4th year. I believe it may take him five years to graduate. He is seeing the sights and sounds of Puebla and nearby Mexico City. He has a Girlfriend named Rose. I have been using our storage room as a sort of research den for Genealogy. I want to thank Familysearch centers, the Newberry Library and also VMI for their help in Family History.

My health has been doing very well this year so far. Not a lot of pain, and improved results on my lab tests. I have been taking daily exercise and walks also. I have developed a taste for Chinese food at the supermercado. They fire it up right! Our cats Nana, Candy & Nieve are pampered daily. When it comes to our cats, TLC is my middle name.

The mean orange cat was removed from the área in Spring when his owner moved away and took him with her. He rode off into the sunset in style!

Jonathan and David Urbina and their families came to visit us from Florida in February. We had wonderful festivities in their honor. Also, Judy threw a fantastic birthday party in July at a party salón in Durango. The beef tacos went down straight!

Garret visited Spain/Morocco in the Spring with Kathy, Hawaii in May with the Family, Acapulco in June, and Colombia in July. It was like an episode out of 'Destinos'. He has been working hard and 'burning the midnight oil' to take those vacations.

Last December, Mayte's friend Lourdes Bustos, from Ecuador, came to visit us. We were able to enjoy a sumptuous, holiday buffet at the Hotel Santa Cruz. Lourdes currently works as a Teacher in Champaign, Illinois.

Tragedy struck the Family on October 23rd when Mayte's Cousin Osiris died in a work-related accident. He was buried in the Panteon Jardin near the airport. He was too young too die- let's put it that way. RIP Osiris.

As far as current events, We support military and humanitarian aid to Isreal. We regret the loss of life in the región. We ask God that He may have mercy on both sides.

In Ukraine, we support continued military and humanitarian aid to Ukraine. The 'breadbasket' of Europe should not be lost. To paraphrase Gen. Ben Hodges, 'the vital terrain in this conflict is Crimea.' We hope that Ukrainians continue to fight for their country and liberty, and perhaps even the Russian guerilla groups (i.e. Freedom of Russia Legion, etc.) can help too. Slava Ukrayini!

25 years ago, I was discharged from the Marine Corps and was able to parlay with the Ghosts and Goblins that night at a Halloween Party- hayride style! I want to thank the nice female Marine Corporal who helped me catch my flight back home the next morning. Semper Fi to all those Marines out there!

So, we pray for Peace in the World and Good Will among Mankind!

God Bless You and God Bless America!

Brian & Family